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Designing Decision Support System to Select IT Projects and Services (Case Study: Tosan Company)

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Abstract

Nowadays, considering the focus of international community on the field of IT services as well as the move of large organizations toward profitability by providing appropriate services to the needs of organization and business markets, it is necessary to draw more consideration to the related projects than ever. In this regard, identification and selection of IT services' indicators and evaluation of these services, and projects, are effective methods to increase profitability and effectiveness of IT in organizations. Therefore, in this study, first the effective criteria in selecting IT projects and services identified, and then a decision support system designed based on fuzzy analytical hierarchy process. And also, by applying the proposed system, the analysis was conducted to determine the sensitivity of various criteria against changes and the effects of each on the final ranking results. Finally, comparing the results of the study with others, the advantages of proposed decision support system have been described.

Keywords

Balanced Scorecard; decision support system; Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process; IT services